

Epiphrenic Diverticulum and Zenker's Diverticulum: Simultaneous Double Surgical Approach: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Esophageal diverticula are a rare condition, with an incidence of 0.06 to 4% and can present as pharyngoesophageal (Zenker), mid-esophageal (epibronchial), and/or distal diverticula, the latter also called epiphrenic, representing 15% of all diverticula. The importance of timely diagnosis and treatment lies in reducing complications and, therefore, morbidity.

We present the case of a 74-year-old female patient who, in her diagnostic approach due to a clinical picture of dysphagia, was identified as having the presence of a Zenker's diverticulum and an epiphrenic diverticulum, so she was scheduled for double diverticulectomy, with a conventional cervical approach (open) and a laparoscopic abdominal approach, at UMAE 25 in Monterrey, Nuevo León, México.

KEYWORDS: Zenker's diverticulum, epiphrenic diverticulum, esophageal motility disorders, cervical approach, laparoscopic approach for diverticulum resection.

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INTRODUCTION

Esophageal diverticula are a rare condition, with an incidence of 0.06 to 4% and can present as pharyngoesophageal (Zenker) or mid-esophageal (epibronchial) diverticula, and/or distal diverticula, the latter also called epiphrenic diverticula, representing 15% of all diverticula (1).

Classification

Diverticula can be classified according to their location, mechanism of production, and relationship to the sphincters (2, 3).

Based on their location, they are divided into cervical, thoracic, and abdominal diverticula. Based on their mechanism of production, they are classified as pulsion, traction, or combined. Based on their relationship to the sphincters, they are classified as juxta-sphincteric and extra-sphincteric diverticula (4).

Zenker's Diverticulum

Zenker's, or cricopharyngeal, diverticula are protrusions of the pharyngeal mucosa through a weak area of the posterior wall of the pharynx, known as Killian's triangle, located

between the inferior pharyngeal constrictor muscle and the cricopharyngeus muscle (2).

Clinical Picture

Zenker's diverticulum is characterized by the clinical manifestations of food regurgitation, halitosis, neck mass, and intrinsic and extrinsic dysphagia, manifested by a progressive increase in the diverticulum's volume due to food retention, causing direct compression of the esophagus (2).

The intensity of the symptoms will depend on the size of the diverticulum (2).

Epiphrenic Diverticulum

The epiphrenic diverticulum is a pulsion diverticulum in which the mucosal and submucosal layers herniate through the muscular layers. It is located 10 cm from the esophagogastric junction (5, 6).

They occur mostly on the right posterolateral side of the esophagus and usually measure 1 to 14 cm. Diagnosis requires special studies such as barium esophagram, panendoscopy, esophageal manometry, and computed tomography (7).

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The importance of these diverticula is that they can present complications such as tracheal fistulas, hemorrhage, vocal cord paralysis, foreign body retention, and an increased risk of developing malignancy of up to 0.3% to 7%, 1.8%, and 0.6%, respectively (1).

Pathophysiology of Esophageal Diverticula

In both cases, diverticula are associated with esophageal motility disorders in 75–100% of cases (the most common being achalasia and diffuse esophageal spasm). These symptoms are more associated with the motor disorder than with the presence of the diverticulum (3).

Lack of coordination in the relaxation of either of the esophageal sphincters (upper and lower) leads to increased intraluminal pressure and mucosal protrusion, leading to the formation of diverticula (3).

The diagnosis of esophageal diverticula is based primarily on history taking and radiographic documentation of the diverticulum. Imaging studies used are those that allow the use of contrast material during swallowing, the most commonly used being water-soluble contrast and barium swallows, or fluoroscopy (2).

Treatment of Zenker's diverticulum

Treatment is indicated to relieve the symptoms of dysphagia and regurgitation, and to prevent complications such as aspiration pneumonia and lung abscesses. Currently, there is no treatment of choice; however, two approaches are used: open surgery with upper esophageal sphincter myotomy and diverticulectomy or diverticulopexy, and transoral endoscopic surgery (7, 8, 9).

Epiphrenic Diverticulum Treatment

Treatment is directed at the underlying cause, commonly esophageal motility disorders such as achalasia, which are present in most patients (10).

Treatment options include nonsurgical management for asymptomatic patients or those with smaller diverticula who are not good candidates for surgery. Surgical management is recommended for symptomatic patients with dysphagia, regurgitation, food impaction, or complications such as aspiration pneumonia (11, 12).

The preferred approach is laparoscopic, which generally includes diverticulectomy, a long myotomy, and an antireflux procedure (fundoplication). Myotomy is essential, while diverticulectomy is not always necessary. Another alternative, per-oral endoscopic myotomy (POEM), is a novel, effective, and minimally invasive technique that may be an option, especially for patients with achalasia or those who are not suitable for surgery (13, 14, 15).

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 75-year-old female presented with a clinical picture characterized by dysphagia to solids with progression to liquids, regurgitation, and unintentional weight loss of more than 10 kg in 6 months, accompanied by retrosternal pain, for which she came to the clinic for evaluation. Imaging studies

were performed, which included an esophagogastroduodenal (EGGD) series, which showed 2 filling defects, one at the c5-c6 level of 2 cm and another in the distal third with a defect of up to 1 cm (Figures 1 and 2).

FIGURE 1. Esophago-gastro-duodenal series, epiphrenic diverticulum is observed, 6.8 cm from the LES, measuring 2 x 1 cm.

FIGURE 2. Epiphrenic diverticulum and Zenker's diverticulum, anteroposterior view.

The protocol was completed with manometry and panendoscopy. Panendoscopy revealed a lower esophageal diverticulum measuring approximately 15 mm at 38 cm from the dental arch, chronic pangastroscopy, and type II diaphragmatic opening.

Esophageal manometry showed a normotonic upper esophageal sphincter with coordinated relaxation, an esophageal body with peristaltic waves of normal amplitude and displacement, and a normotonic lower esophageal sphincter.

Based on the clinical findings, a preoperative Eckardt score of 4 points was assigned.

Once the surgical protocol was completed, a decision was made to perform the procedure, using a simultaneous double surgical approach, with a conventional cervical approach (open) and a laparoscopic abdominal approach.

Cervical Approach:

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The patient is in the supine position, with cervical hyperextension, the neck lateralized to the right, exposing the left hemineck. After cervical marking, a 5-cm incision is made anterior to the left sternocleidomastoid muscle. The dissection is continued in layers up to the platysma muscle, which is incised. The omohyoid muscle, internal jugular vein, and carotid artery are identified, which are lateralized. The dissection and division of the middle thyroid vein and inferior thyroid artery are continued with advanced energy, locating Zenker's diverticulum in Killian's triangle, approaching the tracheoesophageal groove. A circumferential dissection of the vascular pedicle is performed. Subsequently, a 4 cm cricopharyngeal myotomy was performed with monopolar energy, achieving release of the diverticulum. A diverticulectomy was performed with a gold cartridge stapler, extracting a 2.5 by 2 cm piece, staging LAHEY 2 (MORTON 2). The absence of a leak was confirmed by instilling methylene blue through a nasogastric tube. Once hemostasis was confirmed, the wound was approached in layers, deep plane and platysma with 3-0 absorbable suture with a continuous surge and skin with subdermal (Figure 3).

FIGURE 3. Zenker's diverticulum, left lateral cervical approach.

Transabdominal laparoscopic approach:

The trocar insertion site is infiltrated with bupivacaine, a left paraumbilical incision is made, a pneumoperitoneum is insufflated using a closed technique to 12 mm Hg, a 12 mm optical trocar is inserted, and the patient is placed in the Trendelenburg position.

A second 10 mm port is placed in the left flank along the midclavicular line, a third 5 mm port is placed in the right flank along the midclavicular line, a fourth 5 mm port is placed in the left flank along the anterior axillary line, and a fifth 5 mm port is placed subxiphoid for the insertion of a liver retractor. The gastrohepatic ligament is dissected with advanced energy and towards the cephalad to the right pillar, the dissection is continued circumferentially, releasing the left pillar until completing the retrosophageal window, a retrosophageal Penrose is placed in the thoracic esophagus to perform traction on the upper lateral face and perform a circumferential dissection of the esophagus, identifying an increase in volume on the right lateral face suggestive of a lower esophageal diverticulum (Figure 4), dissecting its neck to subsequently perform a diverticulectomy with a 60mm lapar stapler (Figure 5), obtaining a 3.5 x 2 cm piece (Figure

6), continuing with a proximal 5 cm ipsilateral myotomy. Subsequently, the diaphragmatic pillars are plicated on the posterior face with 2-0 non-absorbable suture.

FIGURE 4. Intraoperative image of the left anterior cervical region of the carotid triangle, following tumor resection. The common carotid artery (yellow), internal carotid artery (blue), and external carotid artery (green) are observed.

FIGURE 5. Surgical piece.

FIGURE 6. Findings consistent with benign carotid paraganglioma, with no histological criteria for malignancy.

DISCUSSION

Epiphrenic esophageal diverticulum and Zenker's diverticulum, despite being rare conditions with a reported prevalence of 0.0015% to 2% and 0.01% to 0.11%, respectively, in the general population, can cause significant morbidity if not treated promptly.

Currently, there is no literature reporting the coexistence of these two diverticula, so we estimate that the incidence and prevalence of both are even lower than previously described.

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Multiple management options have been described for esophageal diverticula, with specific indications for each. Therefore, the location, size, distance from the hiatus (in epiphrenic diverticula), as well as the association with esophageal motility disorders, should be considered. In our case, given that we had two diverticula in different locations in the esophagus, we decided to perform a simultaneous double approach, opting for a conventional cervical approach for the management of Zenker's diverticulum. In the case of the epiphrenic diverticulum, we decided to perform a transabdominal laparoscopic approach, as it has been described as the most accepted to date. Currently, there is no consensus on which approach to use.

For Zenker's diverticulum, both endoscopic and open approaches have been proposed. In endoscopic surgery, the septum (and cricopharyngeal muscle) is divided between the diverticulum and the esophageal lumen to facilitate bolus passage (7).

Furthermore, this is indicated for diverticula with an average size of 3 to 5 cm, which allows for easy placement of the endostapler and adequate myotomy of the cricopharyngeal muscle. Its advantages include shorter procedure times, early return to oral intake, shorter hospital stays, and faster recovery (8, 9).

And in the open approach, which we chose because it was the most effective when deciding on a simultaneous approach, excision and myotomy are performed, especially in large diverticula, in young patients, or when there is suspicion of coexisting carcinoma in the diverticulum. Open myotomy alone is probably the most effective and safe procedure for very small diverticula, especially those smaller than 2 cm. The main complication of this method is suture line leakage. However, modern stapling devices have decreased its incidence, and this complication did not occur in this clinical case (7, 8, 9).

Therefore, we can conclude that both access routes are safe for Zenker's diverticulum and provide similarly good results. No significant differences in effectiveness, symptom recurrence, and/or postoperative complications are reported in the literature (9).

Regarding epiphrenic diverticulum, articles do mention better results with laparoscopic surgery, which was chosen in our clinical case, performing a diverticulectomy and myotomy with fundoplication. The results were good postoperatively and had good long-term results (11, 12, 13).

CONCLUSION

Esophageal diverticula are rare, with diverse clinical presentations depending on location, size, and the presence of adjacent diseases or motility disorders. However, their importance lies in the morbidity and decreased quality of life caused by their symptoms, as well as the complications they can cause. Selecting the appropriate surgical treatment with good results is essential for this pathology, especially in cases where several diverticula coexist. Opting for simultaneous

approaches that combine the best surgery for each diverticulum is essential. As in this clinical case, choosing a laparoscopic approach for the epiphrenic diverticulum and an open approach for the Zenker diverticulum was a good surgical option.

ABBREVIATIONS: esophagogastroduodenal (EGGD), lower esophageal sphincter (LES)

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